

THE PRESENCE OF RADIOACTIVE ISOTOPES IN ENVIRONMENTAL SOIL SAMPLE AND RADIOCHEMICAL SEPARATION OF ALPHA - EMITTING ISOTOPES AS PART OF THEIR DETERMINATION'S PROCEDURE

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Abstract

Radioactive isotopes are present in soil either naturally or due to human activities. The isotopes originated from the uranium and thorium decay chains, can modify soil properties, water quality, and potentially enter in the food chain. The most common naturally occurring radioactive isotopes are Uranium - 238, Thorium -232 and Potassium - 40. The natural radioactivity of the soil is determined from the mineral composition of the rocks. Rocks with high concentrations of uranium, thorium, and potassium will produce soils with higher radioactivity. Radioactive contamination can impact soil properties, potentially affecting plant growth and overall ecosystem health. The procedures for the determination of alpha emitting isotopes in soil, generally follow these two steps: 1. Sample preparation which includes dissolution (using a mixture of hydrofluoric and nitric acids to release the radioisotopes) and separation (using different techniques like coprecipitation, ion-exchange, liquid-liquid extraction, extraction chromatography) to isolate the specific alpha-emitting isotopes from the dissolved sample. 2. Alpha Spectrometry measurement (separated isotopes are deposited on a stainless-steel disk and measured using an alpha spectrometer). The aim of this paper is to describe in detail the procedure applied in the radiochemistry laboratory of the IANP for the sample preparation and separation of alpha emitters in environmental soil sample. This optimal procedure is the result of evaluating each step of the procedure performed in years in the laboratory.

Keywords: radiochemical preparation, alpha emitters, radioactive isotopes, separation technique.

Introduction

The vast majority detected on the earth is from the natural radioactivity from primordial origins [1,2]. Uranium in nature is one of the heaviest elements that exists mainly in the earth crust and its activity is found in soil, in water and/or in the earth-born materials [1,2]. Uranium is found as ²³⁸U (99.2739 - 99.2752%), has occurred in many different rock types from sedimentary to volcanic and has been deposited on land by volcanic action [2]. Chemical conditions sometimes elevate the concentrations of uranium, and significantly occur in some substances such as phosphate rock deposits, minerals (such as lignite) and monazite sands in uranium-rich ores [3]. The redistribution of uranium in soil, rocks as well as in water is happening throughout the environment by wind, rain and geologic processes. Moreover, it can dissolve in the water to be consumed by any organism [2]. The mean concentration of ²³⁸U in the earth's crust varies from 0.5 to 5 ppm, and in granite it is 4 ppm [2].

The radioactive substance of thorium occurs naturally in the earth's crust in combination with other minerals such as silica. More than 99% of natural thorium exists in the form of thorium - 232 with a concentration range of 2 - 20 ppm [2,3]. Some rocks in underground mines contain more concentrated form of thorium. Natural weathering like wind and water action breaks these rocks and makes the thorium and all other components of the rocks to become a part of the soil. Moreover, the soil containing high amount of clay materials show higher contents of thorium [2]. The two natural isotopes of potassium ³⁹K (93.2581%) and ⁴¹K (6.7302%) are needed for living species, however, the strong gamma radiation emitted from the primordial ⁴⁰K causes various health hazards [1,2].

The radionuclides and their progenies are the principal contributor to the background radiation in our living environment. The different physio-chemical forms

of these radionuclides have influenced their mobility and biological uptake. As for instance, uranium specially bonds to organic matter while potassium and thorium preferentially bond to clays, and hence these are more radioactive than the other sedimentary rocks [2,3].

Radioisotopes are of interest in environmental physics for several reasons:

- Environmental protection - the emitted radiation is potentially hazardous and therefore radioactivity levels in environmental media must be monitored and the consequences of contaminations have to be assessed [1].
- Tracing - as the detection limits can be very low, radioisotopes can be used successfully as tracers to monitor e.g., transport processes [4].
- Dating - due to the ubiquity and the wide range of half - life times of naturally occurring radioisotopes, they can be used for age determination [1].

Material and Methods

Analytical procedure for separation and quantification of ²¹⁰Po, ²⁴¹Am, Pu and U isotopes by extraction chromatography and alpha spectrometry is described as follows [5,6].

1. Sample preparation (dispensing and dissolution):

Dispense ~ 1g of the sediment to a 50 mL screw-cup centrifuge tube, record the sample weight, add 70.1Bq of ²⁰⁹Po, ²⁴³Am, ²³²U and ²⁴²Pu tracers and record the added weight of each tracer solutions. Add 20mL of concentration HNO₃ to dissolve the sediment and after dissolution evaporate to dryness and re-dissolve in 15 mL of 0.1M HNO₃. For Calcium phosphate co-precipitation add 0.2mL of 30% H₂O₂ to ensure Po (IV), 1 mL 1.25M calcium nitrate (50 mg Ca) and 3 mL 3.2M ammonium hydrogen phosphate. Adjust the pH

to pH 10 with concentrated ammonium hydroxide using a pink phenolphthalein end point. Centrifuge at 3500 rpm for 6 min, discard the supernatant, add 10 mL of 8M HNO₃ / 3 mL of 2M Al(NO₃)₃ to dissolve the precipitate and add 0.1 mL of 30% H₂O₂ to ensure Po (IV) [5,6].

2. TRU/DGA separation:

For TRU/DGA cartridge separation, attach stacked TRU/DGA cartridges to the vacuum box loaded with 50 mL test tubes, precondition the resin by passing 20 mL of 8M HNO₃, load the sample to the top

of the stacked cartridges, rinse with 10 mL of 8M HNO₃ to fix Am, Po, U, Pu on the resin and to remove matrix interferences. Then, rinse with 10 mL of 10M HNO₃ to transfer Po to the DGA and rinse the cartridge tandem with 15 mL of 4M HCl to transfer Am to the DGA resin. Separate TRU from DGA cartridges, add clean reservoirs. Elute Pu from TRU as Pu (III) with 12 mL 3M HCl - 0.02M TiCl₃. Elute U from TRU with 15 mL 0.1M Ammonium oxalate. Elute Am from DGA with 12 mL 0.25M HCl. Elute Po from DGA with 15 mL 0.05M HNO₃ [5,6].

Results and Discussions

The optimal procedure described in the above section is the result of the many experiments performed in different conditions including all the steps of the procedure.

The results for the separation of alpha emitters (210Po, 241Am, Pu and U) are analyzed and discussed in detail and each step of the procedure that is performed in a different way to find optimal and good separation of each radioisotope.

Micro-precipitation of Plutonium

Add 10 mL of water to reduce the acid strength and 0.5 mL 30% H₂O₂ to oxidize any that might be present to prevent uranium co-precipitation. After that add 50 ug Ce and 2 mL 28 M HF to form CeF₃. Wait 15 min and filter the solution using a 25 mm polypropylene Resolve filter. Rinse the filter with 5 mL deionized water and 5 mL ethanol. Dry the filter under a heat lamp for a couple of minutes.

Micro-precipitation of Uranium

Add 0.5 mL 10% TiCl₃ to reduce U(VI) to U(IV) and 50 ug Ce and 1 mL 28 M HF to form CeF₃. Wait 15 min and filter the solution using a 25 mm polypropylene Resolve filter. Rinse the filter with 5 mL deionized water and 5 mL ethanol. Dry the filter under a heat lamp for a couple of minutes.

Micro-precipitation of Americium

Add 0.2 mL of 30% H₂O₂ to oxidize any that might be present to prevent uranium co-precipitation and 50 ug Ce and 1 mL 28 M HF to form CeF₃. Wait 15 min and filter the solution using a 25 mm polypropylene

Resolve filter. Rinse the filter with 5 mL deionized water and 5 mL ethanol. Dry the filter under a heat lamp for a couple of minutes.

Micro-precipitation of Polonium

Add 0.1 mL of 30% H₂O₂ to ensure Po (IV) and 100 ug Bi (0.1 mL of 1000 ppm Bi standard in 2 % HNO₃). Adjust the pH adding 0.2 mL of 3M NH₄OH (ammonia solution). Add 0.8 mL of 3.2M NH₄H₂PO₄ to form BiPO₄ precipitate and mix well by shaking for a couple of minutes. Wait 15 min and filter the solution using a 25 mm polypropylene Resolve filter. Rinse the filter with 5 mL deionized water and 5 mL ethanol and dry the filter under a heat lamp for a couple of minutes.

Conclusions and Recommendations

In order to find a good correlation between water quality, used for drinking and hygienic purposes, and the milk quality, more extensive studies are necessary, including a big number of samples and farms to be taken into study as well as identification of specific microorganisms.

The studies allow determining the concentration and spread of radionuclides in the soil.

Contaminated soils treated with an acid solution of ions NO₃⁻, PO₄⁻⁻⁻ and K⁺, undergo a reduction of radioactivity up to 35%, after a series of washes which simulate one year's rainfall.

The capacity of the deepest soil layers to immobilize the radionuclides percolated from the superficial layers was also confirmed.

The migration of radionuclides towards deeper soil layers, following chemical treatments, and their subsequent stabilization reduces bioavailability in the

uppermost soil horizon, preventing at the same time their transfer into the water-bearing stratum.

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